

The Influence Of Transformational Leadership and Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance of PT.SAT with Work Motivation as an Intervening Variable

¹Nabila Ramadhani Putri, ²Dewi Prihatini, ³Sri Wahyu Lelly H.S

¹Postgraduate Student, ^{2,3}Postgraduate Lecturer
Faculty of Economics and Business
University of Jember, Jember, Indonesia

Abstract- This research aims to analyze the influence of transformational leadership and emotional intelligence on PT.SAT employee performance with work motivation as an intervening variable. This research was conducted on PT.SAT focus store employees. Population of 241 employees. The sample size was determined using the Slovin formula with an error tolerance limit of 5%, so there were 150 employees to be respondents. The sampling technique use proportionate stratified random sampling. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents. The data source used is a primary data source. The analysis method uses SEM analysis with the measurement tool using SmartPLS. The results of the research on the direct influence test showed that transformational leadership had a positive and significant influence on work motivation and performance, emotional intelligence had a positive and significant influence on work motivation and performance, work motivation had a positive and significant influence on performance and in the results of the indirect influence test there were motivation results. can mediate transformational leadership on performance and motivation can mediate emotional intelligence on performance.

Keyword- Transformational Leadership, Emotional Intelligence, Work Motivation, Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

PT.SAT Jember branch, especially in stores referred to as focus stores which have employees with the positions of store head, assistant store head and store crew. They are the spearhead of the PT.SAT company in terms of providing sales services to consumers, so that whether the company's performance is good or not can be seen from the performance of employees in providing services to consumers to achieve their targets. Good and consistent performance is needed in providing services to consumers to achieve the work targets of the plans that have been set. One of the factors that influences employee performance is leadership. Becker (2011) states that leadership is the main factor in subordinates' self-development, encouraging subordinates to think and act innovatively to solve problems and achieve goals. One leadership style that influences employee performance is transformational leadership. This is in accordance with the research results of Ahmad Prayudi (2020), which shows that there is a significant influence between transformational leadership and performance. Another factor that influences performance is emotional intelligence. According to Hamzah (2008) emotional intelligence is the ability of employees to motivate themselves in facing challenges and the ability to manage emotions well. Emotional intelligence is essential in improving individual performance at work as it helps in building strong relationships, managing conflict, motivating oneself and others, managing stress, and making better decisions. This is in accordance with the results of research by Evita and Rusman (2022) that employee emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Employees need to have motivation to work to achieve goals. According to Usman (2013: 276) motivation is the force that encourages someone to carry out an action or deed. Motivation according to Maslow in Sutrisno (2014:55) is a factor that gives energy and enthusiasm to someone to work together, work effectively, and integrate all their efforts in achieving satisfaction at work. Based on the description of several empirical studies as well as research gaps and phenomena that exist at PT.SAT Jember branch, it can be explained that factors such as transformational leadership and emotional intelligence, whose influence can be seen through employee work motivation, are variables that can shape employee performance. With this in mind, this research will examine "the influence of transformational leadership and emotional intelligence on the performance of PT.SAT Jember branch employees with work motivation being an intervening variable.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

Robin (2007), transformational leadership is a leader who devotes his attention to the problems faced by his followers and the development needs of each of his followers by providing enthusiasm and encouragement to achieve his goals. There are indicators of transformational leadership :

1. Idealized influence is the leader's ability to act as a role model for employees at work.
2. Intellectual stimulation is giving direction by the leadership to employees to be more innovative and creative in their work.
3. Individual Consideration is attention by leaders to employees to achieve good performance.
4. Inspirational motivation is the ability of leaders to encourage employees to always be optimistic in achieving good work.

Emotional Intelligence

Goleman in Noor Ali (2017:2) states that emotional intelligence is the ability to monitor and control one's own and other people's feelings and use these feelings to guide thoughts and actions, so that emotional intelligence is very necessary for success at work and producing outstanding performance. in work The following indicators of Emotional intelligence are:

1. Self-awareness is the employee's ability to understand the mood they feel while working.
2. Emotional regulation is the employee's ability to manage moods so as not to get caught up in emotions.
3. Self-motivation is the employee's ability to generate encouragement to do something more productive.
4. Empathy is an employee's ability to feel what other people are experiencing.
5. Building relationships is the employee's ability to interact and communicate with other people.

Performance

Koopmans (2014) Performance is defined as individual behavior or actions that are in accordance with organizational goals. The following performance indicators are:

1. Task performance is the employee's ability to make a work plan from predetermined work tasks.
2. Contextual performance is the employee's ability to take the initiative in carrying out work tasks that have not been completed in the work team.
3. Counterproductive behavior is employee behavior that is less productive at work.

Work Motivation

According to Cook (2016) motivation is a process that focuses on a goal and it will be related to the initiation and continuation of activities aimed at achieving that goal. Motivation indicators are as follows:

1. The need for achievement (Need for Achievement) is the need for employees to be successful so that they make efforts to achieve achievements at work.
2. The need for affiliation (Affiliation Need) is the employee's need to have good relations with other people.
3. Need for Power is an employee's need for high power to have influence on other people.

Reasearch Conseptual Framework

Figure 1. Concept Framework

Keterangan:

- > : direct effect
 - - - - -> : indirect effect

H1: Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on the work motivation

According to Robin (2007), transformational leadership is a leader who focuses his attention on the problems faced by his followers and the development needs of each follower by providing enthusiasm and encouragement to achieve goals. This shows that transformational leadership can be an influence on employee work motivation. In accordance with Putra's (2019) research, transformational leadership has a positive effect on employee work motivation. Apart from that, it is also in accordance with Agustian's (2023) research that transformational leadership has a significant positive effect on work motivation.

H2: Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on the performance

According to Robin (2007), transformational leadership is a leader who devotes his attention to the problems faced by his followers and the development needs of each of his followers by providing enthusiasm and encouragement to achieve his goals. This shows that transformational leadership can be an influence on employee work motivation. This shows that transformational leadership can be an influence on employee work motivation. In accordance with research from Martha (2020), transformational leadership has a significant effect on employee performance and is also supported by research from Saputro (2021) that Transformational Leadership has a significant effect on employee performance.

H3: Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on the work motivation

Emotional intelligence is the intelligence a person has to motivate themselves in facing failure and controlling emotions, as well as delaying gratification in managing mental states (Tridhonanto, 2010). This shows that emotional intelligence can influence work motivation, which is in accordance with Calvin's (2021) research. Apart from that, according to Sinta (2021), emotional intelligence has a significant effect on work motivation.

H4: Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on the performance

Emotional intelligence is the intelligence a person has to motivate themselves in facing failure and controlling emotions, as well as delaying gratification in managing mental states (Tridhonanto, 2010). This means that emotional intelligence can improve performance because it can regulate emotions at work. Maheswari's (2022) previous research stated that emotional intelligence has a significant effect on performance. Supported by other research, namely from the research results of Wahyudi (2022), emotional intelligence has a significant effect on employee performance.

H5: Work Motivation has a significant effect on the performance

Winardi (2016) states that motivation is the potential strength of an individual and is developed by external things such as encouragement in the form of financial and non-financial rewards so that it has an impact on work results positively and otherwise. In previous research from Marlius (2023) work motivation influenced employee performance. And supported by research by Fernos (2023) that work motivation influences employee performance.

H6: Work motivation can mediate transformational leadership on the performance

Malay (2015) opinion that motivation relate with excitement employee work level lower with give ability And Skills Which maximum For objective company. In Ardana's research (2020) Positive work motivation and significant in mediating the influence of transformational leadership to performance employee. Apart from that, it is supported by other research, namely from Prayudi's (2020) research. Work motivation can mediate the influence of transformational leadership on employee performance.

H7: Work motivation can mediate emotional intelligence on the performance

Merihot (in Marlioni, 2015) explain that motivation directing employee behavior in completing a job with form business Which enthusiastic. in study Utami (2018) that motivation work can be done mediate emotional intelligence on employee performance . Apart from that, there is other research from Cahyaningsih (2019) that work motivation can mediate the influence of *emotional intelligence* on employee performance.

III. RESEARCH METHODS***Population and Sample***

The population that was the research object was focus store employees at PT. SAT Jember branch has 241 employees from 24 focus store outlets. The number of samples was obtained from the Slovin formula with an error rate of 5%, so the samples was 150 respondents. Proportionate Stratified Random Sampling was used for the sampling technique.

Analysis Technique

The sample in this study was 150 samples, so data analysis used partial least squares (PLS). Kock and Hadaya (2018) stated that with a significance level of 5% research can use a sample size of up to 155 samples. Partial least squares (PLS) is a form of structural equation model (SEM) analysis method that uses the VB-SEM (variance based-structural equation modeling) approach. The partial least squares (PLS) method is a predictive technique that can handle many independent variables, even if multicollinearity occurs between these variables.

Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The measurement model or outer model aims to specify the relationship between latent variables and their indicators. The indicator is declared valid when it has an outer loading value above 0.5. After knowing the results of the outer loading, you can continue to test discriminant validity with Fornell-Lacker and cross loading. When the correlation of a construct with a measurement item is greater than other constructs, it can be stated that the latent construct predicts the measure in the block better than the others. Another method that is looked at is to look at the reliability of a construct, namely by measuring composite reliability and Cronbach alpha.

Structural Model (Inner Model)

Structural models or inner models are used to predict relationships between latent variables or variables that cannot be measured directly. In the structural model, carry out a multicollinearity test to find out if a regression model finds a correlation between variables. The test can use the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) Test. If the value is less than 5 then this shows that there are no problems between the independent variables or that multicollinearity does not occur.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first test in SmartPLS is to analyze the outer model first, this aims to find out how well the variables represent the variables being measured. The measurements used consist of convergent validity tests, discriminant validity tests and reliability tests.

Outer Model Analysis

a. Convergent Validity

The convergent validity measurement of the measurement model with reflective indicators can be seen from the correlation between the item scores and the construct scores. To test convergent validity, outer loading is used. An indicator is considered valid if it has an outer loading value > 0.7 . However, at the research stage of scale development, loadings of 0.50 to 0.60 were still acceptable (Ghozali, 35:2021). So this research uses the middle value of this theory, namely 0.6. The results of the outer loading analysis:

Table 1. Convergent Validity

Variabel	Indikator	Loading factor	Hasil
Transformational Leadership	X1.1	0,818	Valid
	X1.2	0,882	Valid
	X1.3	0,880	Valid
	X1.4	0,869	Valid
Emotional Intelligence	X2.1	0,727	Valid
	X2.2	0,765	Valid
	X2.3	0,825	Valid
	X2.4	0,759	Valid
	X2.5	0,848	Valid
Motivation	Z1	0,807	Valid
	Z2	0,877	Valid
	Z3	0,828	Valid
Performance	Y1	0,868	Valid
	Y2	0,826	Valid
	Y3	0,761	Valid

Sources: Result of data processing, 2023

Based on the first data processing with the transformational leadership variable with 4 indicators, the loading factor results were > 0.6 , which means it is valid. The emotional intelligence variable with 5 indicators results in a loading factor > 0.6 , which means it is valid. Motivation variable with 3 indicators results in loading factor > 0.6 . Performance variable with 3 indicators results in loading factor > 0.6 . This means that the validity of the loading factor is met and can be carried out to the next stage.

b. Discriminant Validity

The discriminant validity test is assessed based on the cross loading of the measurement with the variables. Based on the PLS output, the cross loading values are obtained as follows:

Tabel 2. Cross Loading

Indikator	Transformational Leadership	Emotional Intelligence	Performance	Motivation
X1.1	0.818	0.475	0.513	0.443
X1.2	0.882	0.531	0.616	0.531
X1.3	0.880	0.472	0.560	0.513
X1.4	0.869	0.489	0.696	0.513
X2.1	0.502	0.727	0.493	0.490
X2.2	0.426	0.765	0.515	0.515
X2.3	0.446	0.825	0.679	0.635
X2.4	0.418	0.759	0.544	0.485
X2.5	0.462	0.848	0.632	0.659
Y1	0.466	0.681	0.868	0.625
Y2	0.391	0.620	0.826	0.655
Y3	0.825	0.510	0.761	0.531
Z1	0.417	0.570	0.555	0.807
Z2	0.564	0.661	0.668	0.877
Z3	0.470	0.564	0.620	0.828

Sources: Result of data processing, 2023

Based on the cross loading results in table 2, X1 is an indicator of the transformational leadership variable, X2 is emotional intelligence, Z is motivation, and Y is employee performance. Based on the cross loading table above, it can be concluded that each indicator in a latent variable has a higher cross loading value in its own construct so that it can be concluded that all variables have met the discriminant validity test.

c. Cronbach Alpha

Table 3. Cronbach Alpha

Variable	CA	Result
Transformational Leadership	0,885	Very Reliabel
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	0,845	Very Reliabel
Performance	0,754	Reliabel
Motivation	0,788	Reliabel

Sources: Result of data processing, 2023

Based on the results of the Cronbach alpha reliability test, it can be seen that the Cronbach alpha value of each research variable is > 0.7, meaning that the performance and motivation variables are in the reliable category and the transformational leadership and emotional intelligence variables are in the very reliable category.

d. **Composite Reliability**

Table 4. Composite Reliability

Variable	CR	Result
Transformational Leadership	0,921	Reliabel
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	0,890	Reliabel
Performance	0,860	Reliabel
Motivation	0,702	Reliabel

Sources: Result of data processing, 2023

Based on the results of the composite reliability test, it can be seen that all variables are above the value of 0.70. This value states that the variable has a good reliability value in accordance with the required minimum value limit.

Inner Model Analysis

After testing the outer model, then test the structural model or inner model. Inner model or structural model testing is used to see the relationship between construct variables. The analysis carried out first is testing the VIF and finally testing the path coefficient (Path Coefficient) to measure the significance of the magnitude of the influence so that hypothesis testing can be carried out which then tests the direct relationship (direct effect) and indirect relationship (indirect effect). So that later it can be explained type of mediation.

Figure 2. Inner Model Test Results

a. **Multicollinearity Test**

The multicollinearity test was carried out to determine the relationship between indicators. To find out if formative indicators experience multicollinearity, namely by knowing the VIF (variance inflation factors) value. A VIF value below 5 can be said to mean that the indicator does not have multicollinearity. The following are the results of the multicollinearity test:

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test

Variabel	VIF
Transformational Leadership	1,630
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	2,217
Motivation	2,261

Sources: Result of data processing, 2023

Based on the multicollinearity test, it shows that the VIF value is below 5, so it can be said that there is no multicollinearity for each of the research variables.

b. Direct Effect Test

From the results of the research hypothesis testing model using SmartPLS, the direct influence and indirect influence of the relationship between the variables can be seen. The results of direct influence testing can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Direct Effect Test

	H	Significant	T Statistik	T Tabel	P Values	Result
X1 -> Z	H1	0.256	2.966	1.967	0.000	Positive and Significant
X1 -> Y	H2	0.331	3.855	1.967	0.001	Positive and Significant
X2 -> Z	H3	0.570	7.479	1.967	0.001	Positive and Significant
X2 -> Y	H4	0.325	3.595	1.967	0.000	Positive and Significant
Z -> Y	H5	0.311	2.662	1.967	0.003	Positive and Significant

Sources: Result of data processing, 2023

Based on table 6 regarding the results of direct influence testing, it can be seen that:

1. The influence of Transformational Leadership on employee work motivation Based on the results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $2.966 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$. The transformational leadership variable has an influence of 0.256. So the results show that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on motivation. So it can be concluded that H1 is accepted.
2. The influence of transformational leadership on employee performance Based on the results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $3.855 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.001 \leq 0.05$. The transformational leadership variable has an influence of 0.331. So the results show that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on performance. So it can be concluded that H2 is accepted.
3. The influence of emotional intelligence on motivation Based on the results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $7.479 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.001 \leq 0.05$. The emotional intelligence variable has an influence of 0.570. So the results show that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on motivation. So it can be concluded that H3 is accepted.
4. The influence of emotional intelligence on performance Based on the results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $3.595 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$. The emotional intelligence variable has an influence of 0.325. So the results show that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance. So it can be concluded that H4 is accepted.
5. The influence of motivation on performance Based on the results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $2.662 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.003 \leq 0.05$. The motivation variable has an influence of 0.311. So the results show that motivation has a positive and significant effect on performance. So it can be concluded that H5 is accepted.

c. Indirect Effect Test

Testing the indirect effect can be seen from the indirect effect bootstrapping technique. The results of the indirect influence can be seen in the following table:

Table 7. Indirect Effect Test

	H	Besar pengaruh	T Statistik	T-tabel	P values	Result
X1 -> Z -> Y	H6	0,080	2,437	1,96	0,015	Positive and Significant
X2 -> Z -> Y	H7	0,177	2,555	1,96	0,011	Positive and Significant

Sources: Result of data processing, 2023

Based on the results of table 7, it can be seen that:

1. The test results show that a significant effect was found with a t-statistic value of $2.437 \geq t$ -table value of 1.967. It is known that the p-values are $0.015 \leq 0.05$. The motivation variable has a mediating effect of 0.080 between transformational leadership and employee performance. These results state that motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating transformational leadership on employee performance. So it can be concluded that H6 is accepted.
2. The test results show that a significant effect was found with a t-statistic value of $2.555 \geq t$ -table value of 1.967. It is known that the p-values are $0.011 \leq 0.05$. The motivation variable has a mediating effect of 0.177 between emotional intelligence and employee performance. These results state that motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating emotional intelligence on employee performance. So it can be concluded that H7 is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The effect of Transformational Leadership on Work Motivation

Based on the results of transformational leadership testing on work motivation, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $2.966 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$. The transformational leadership variable has an influence of 0.256. The results of this analysis provide information that transformational leadership has a significant and positive direct effect on employee motivation, which means that the stronger the understanding and implementation of transformational leadership, the stronger the work motivation. These results are consistent with previous research conducted by Putra (2019) which stated that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on motivation. This means that good transformational leadership is able to encourage or motivate company employees.

The effect of Transformational Leadership on Performance

Based on the results of testing transformational leadership on performance, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $3.855 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.001 \leq 0.05$. The transformational leadership variable has an influence of 0.331. The results of this analysis provide information that transformational leadership has a significant and positive direct effect on employee performance, which means that transformational leadership plays an important role in the process of improving employee performance. This is proven by Saputro's (2021) research that transformational leadership has a significant and positive effect on performance. When a leader with a transformational style has an effect on the quality of the relationship between the leader and subordinates, it will encourage subordinates to do a good job.

The effect of Emotional Intelligence on Work Motivation

Based on the test results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $7.479 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.001 \leq 0.05$. The emotional intelligence variable has an influence of 0.570. This is in accordance with research by Calvin (2021) that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on work motivation, which means that when employees have the ability to understand feelings and manage their emotions, it will influence employee motivation in doing work.

The effect of Emotional Intelligence on Performance

Based on the test results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $3.595 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.000 \leq 0.05$. The emotional intelligence variable has an influence of 0.325. This reveals that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance. The results of this analysis reveal that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance, which means that when employees have good emotional intelligence it will improve employee performance. In accordance with research by Maheswari (2022), emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. When the level of relationship between emotional intelligence and performance is in a strong and positive relationship, employee performance will increase because employees can control themselves and manage emotions in overcoming problems faced in completing their tasks.

The effect of Work Motivation on Performance

Based on the test results, it can be seen that the t-statistic value is $7.479 \geq t$ table value of 1.967. The p value is $0.003 \leq 0.05$. The motivation variable has an influence of 0.570. This states that motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. In research by Fernos (2023), work motivation has a significant and positive effect on employee performance, which means that employee motivation plays a role in improving performance.

Work motivation mediates transformational leadership on performance

The test results showed that a significant effect was found with a t-statistic value of $2.437 \geq t$ -table value of 1.967. It is known that the p-values are $0.015 \leq 0.05$. The motivation variable has a mediating effect of 0.080 between transformational leadership and employee performance. The results of data analysis state that motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating transformational leadership on employee performance. This research is in line with several previous studies. Prayudi (2020) explains that motivation can mediate the influence of transformational leadership on performance.

Work motivation mediates emotional intelligence on performance

The test results showed that a significant effect was found with a t-statistic value of $2.555 \geq t$ -table value of 1.967. It is known that the p-values are $0.011 \leq 0.05$. The motivation variable has a mediating effect of 0.177 between emotional intelligence and employee performance. It can be stated that work motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating emotional intelligence on employee performance. In accordance with research by Utami (2019), work motivation can mediate the influence of emotional intelligence on employee performance.

V. CLONCUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that the researcher has explained, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Transformational leadership has a significant and positive direct effect on work motivation
2. Transformational leadership has a significant and positive direct effect on employee performance
3. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on work motivation
4. Emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on performance
5. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance
6. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating transformational leadership on employee performance

7. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect in mediating emotional intelligence on employee performance

REFERENCES:

1. Afandi, P. (2021). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia; Teori, Konsep dan Indikator (edisi ke2)*. ZANAF A PUBLISHING
2. Agustian dan Sitorus. 2023. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap Motivasi Kerja dalam Pandangan New Public Management. *Journal of Administration and Educational Management*. Vol. 6, No.1
3. Ahmad Prayudi. 2020. Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap kinerja karyawan dengan motivasi kerja sebagai variabel intervening. *Jurnal Manajemen*. Vol 6 Nomor 2.
4. Aksara Winardi. (2016). *Kepemimpinan dalam Manajemen*. Jakarta: PT. Rineka Cipta.
5. Al. Tridhonanto. 2010. *Meraih Sukses dengan Kecerdasan Emosional*. Jakarta: Gramedia
6. Ali. 2019. Peran Mediasi Motivasi Kerja Pada Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior Pegawai Pemerintah. *Matrik: Jurnal Manajemen*. Vol 13, No.2.
7. Andjarwati, T. (2015). Motivasi dari sudut pandang teori hirarki kebutuhan Maslow, teori dua faktor Herzberg, teori xy Mc Gregor, dan teori motivasi prestasi Mc Clelland. *JMM17: Jurnal Ilmu ekonomi dan manajemen*, 2(01).
8. Calvin. 2021. Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional dan Iklim Organisasi terhadap Motivasi Kerja di PT. Satnusa Persada TBK. *Skripsi. Fakultas Ilmu Sosial. Universitas Putera Batam: Batam*.
9. Cook, D. A., & Artino, A. R. (2016). Motivation to learn: an overview of contemporary theories. *Medical education*, 50(10), 997-1014
10. Dewianawati, M, S. 2022. Pengaruh Kecerdasan emosional, kompetensi, komunikasi dan disiplin kerja terhadap kinerja karyawan. *Jurnal Teknologi dan Manajemen Industri Terapan*. Vol. 1 No. 3
11. Diamantidis, A.D. and Chatzoglou, P. (2019), "Factors affecting employee performance: an empirical approach", *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol. 68 No. 1
12. Edy, Sutrisno. (2016). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: Kencana Prenada Media Group.
13. Fernos dan Putra. 2023. Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja terhadap Kinerja Pegawai pada Dinas Tenaga Kerja dan Perindustrian Kota Padang. *Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan*. Vol.3, No. 2
14. Farida, Hartono. 2015. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia II*. Unmuh Ponorogo Press.
15. Ghozali, Imam. 2016. *Desain Penelitian Kuantitatif dan Kualitatif untuk Akuntansi, Bisnis dan Ilmu Sosial lainnya*. Edisi. Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro. Semarang
16. Hasibuan, Malayu. S. P. (2015). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Jakarta: PT. Bumi
17. Irawanto, Noermijati, dan Prabowo. 2018. The Influence of Transformational Leadership and Work Motivation on Employee Performance mediated by Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Management*, Vol.16, No.1
18. Kasmir. (2019). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia (Teori dan Praktik) (Edisi ke-5)*. PTRAJA GRAFINDO PERSADA.
19. Koopmans, et al. (2014). Improving the individual work performance questionnaire using rasch analysis. *J Appl Meas*, 15(2)
20. Maheswari, R. 2022. Pengaruh Kecerdasan Emosional karyawan terhadap kinerja karyawan PT. Sumber Alfaria Trijaya, tbk wilayah Bandung 2 Cimahi. *Bandung Conference Series: Business and Management*. 10.
21. Martha, K, A. 2020. Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap kinerja karyawan dengan motivasi kerja sebagai variabel mediasi. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*
22. Marliani, R. (2015). *Psikologi Industri dan Organisasi*. Bandung: Pustaka Setia.
23. Osemeke dan Adegboyega. (2017). Critical Review and Comparism between Maslow, Hezberg and McClelland's Theory of Needs. *Funai Journal Of Accounting*. Vol.1 No.1.
24. Putra dan Sudibya. 2019. Pengaruh kepemimpinan transformasional terhadap motivasi kerja dan kinerja karyawan. *E-Jurnal Manajemen*, Vol. 8, No. 6
25. Rini. 2023. Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap Motivasi Kerja dan Kinerja Pegawai Dinas Pemberdayaan Perempuan. *Poma Jurnal: Publish of Management*. Vol 1, No1.
26. Riski, A. 2018. Pengaruh Disiplin Kerja, Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan Kecerdasan Emosional Terhadap Kepuasan dan Kinerja PNS. *Jurnal Smart Study & Managment Research*. Vol XV, No.1.
27. Robbin, Stephen P. (2007). *Perilaku Organisasi*, Edisi Ke sepuluh, Cet 11. Pt Indek.
28. Robbins, P. S dan Judge, T. A. 2017. *Organizational Behaviour*, Edisi 13, Jilid 1, Salemba Empat. Jakarta.
29. Saputro Ropinov. 2021. Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional dan OCB terhadap kinerja karyawan melalui motivasi karyawan. *Jurnal Emba*, Vol.9 No.2
30. Sinta, Ilham, Heikal, Yunita dan Sandi. 2021. Relationship Between Budget Participation, Job Characteristics, Emotional Intelligence and Work Motivation As Mediator Variables to Strengthening User Power Performance: An Emperical Evidence From Indonesia Government. *MORFAI JOURNAL*, Vol.1, No.1
31. Sugiyono. (2016). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*. Bandung: PT Alfabet.
32. Sujana dan Ardana. 2020. Peran Motivasi Kerja Memediasi Pengaruh Kepemimpinan Transformasional terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *E-jurnal Manajemen*, Vol.9, No.3
33. Tzu-Ping. 2023. The effects of teacher's emotional intelligence on team-member exchange and job performance: the moderating role of teacher seniority. *Springer: Current Psychology*.
34. Yunita. 2023. The Effect of Emotional Intelligence and Work Discipline on Performance with Competence as Intervening Variables in Service Civil Servants Public Works and Spatial Planning. *Sinomics Journal*. Vol 2, No3.
35. Yunus, Juned, Karollah dan Ibrahim. 2022. The Effect of Transformational Leadership, Work Motivation and Culture on Millennial Generation Employees Performance of the Manufacturing Industry in the Digital Era. *Frontiers in Psychology*. Vol. 13